

Chests, sacks and cases: the storage of arms and armour in the Middle Ages

Pavel K. Alekseychik / Medieval Advisor 2022
ORCID 0000-0002-4081-3917

Figure 1. 1300-1325 France, BNF Français 12558, 143v. - Chevalier au Cygne / Chanson d'Antioche. The knights in a military camp are engaged in a game of chess next to their armour. The helmets are stacked on a chest which was possibly used for their transportation; the equipment was taken out of the containers, possibly as preparation for sudden attack.

Medieval military equipment was more than the shine of steel, gold and gemstones – for most of the time, it was a collection of items requiring proper storage. As we admire the depictions of arms and armour in the medieval art, it is easy to forget that all military gear was kept in a variety of containers and covers intended to protect it from the elements, bumpy roads and insects. However, this hidden aspect of the medieval material culture was very important as it ensured long-term preservation of the arms which tended to be rather expensive. Therefore, it would be of interest to compile the written sources on what kinds of containers and covers were used, and what materials were used in their manufacture. This article reviews the mentions of containers used for the storage and transport of armour and weapons from a range of administrative records and knightly romances dating to the late 12th - early 15th century, and the few available visual sources.

High-profile weapons received the best treatment, and were kept in beautiful cases, optionally wrapped in silk. The *chansons de geste* are prone to describing the most impressive of those; we read about a prized sword wrapped in cendal silk in Perceval (ca. 1180-1190)¹, and a similar use of a “rich cloth” in Roman de Berinus (ca. 1350-1370)². An outer rigid cover was of course also needed; In Orendel (ca. 1196), a high-quality sword is kept in its own case (*lade*), which is closed with three ties or clasps³. A kind of specialized case for knives, daggers and swords was called *cultellerium*. In a 1240 will from Genoa, there is a mention of a special case for knives or longer bladed weapons or tools, *cultelleriam cum duobus cultellis*⁴. *Cultelleria* could also have a meaning of a sword-case. The inventory of Pope Calixtinus III (1458) lists three such cases, the first of which contained five gilded swords, in another there were four swords with handles of gilded silver, and the third contained four swords with white handles⁵. In Huon de Bourdele (mid-13th c.), a valuable sword with inscription is kept in its own chest (*escriin*)⁶. King John’s battle axe was stored in a special case, ordered by the King in 1213, “For an iron-bound case for the axe of the lord King, 11 d.”⁷

Knightly helmets and helms were stored and transported in special containers, generally termed in French *heaumier*, although *frambail* was also used. *Heaumier* appears in Aliscans (ca. 1180)⁸, Guillaume de Dole (ca. 1209)⁹, and Romance of Alexander (ca. 1185)¹⁰. *Frambail* can be found in Guillaume de Dole (1200-1225)¹¹.

¹ Roman de Lancelot, vv. 32591-32593 *Qui l'espee avoit aportee / Si l'a prise et envelope / En j. cendal...*

² Roman de Berinus, 263: *bonne espee, envelopee en un chier paille*

³ Orendel (XII, 13-15): *Ein lade im her fur bringen/ Bit drin sluzeln hi si ersloz ... Dar uz nam hi sciere / Ein swert harde ziere*

⁴ Robert S. Lopez, Studi sull'economia genovese nel medio evo, in Documenti e studi per la storia del commercio e del diritto commerciale italiano 8 (Torino: S. Lattes, 1936), pp. 245-47. Archival citation provided by Lopez: AS Genova, Cartulario del Not. Giovanni Enrico De Porta, I, fol. 234 r.

⁵ *Tria Cultelleria, in una vero quinque gladii albi deaurati, in alia quatuor cum manicis de argento deaurato et in alia quatuor cum manicis albis*

⁶ The Tours manuscript of Huon de Bourdele, fol. 129r, v. 21-24: *A son escriin est maintenant ales / Si en trait fors .j. branc d'acher letre...*

⁷ Misae Roll 1212-1213, p. 235, *Pro forello ligato ferro ad unam Hachiam domini Regis facendum xi d.*

⁸ Aliscans, (1180) *En ces hiaumieres ont ces hiaumes poses* (v. 3065).

⁹ Guillaume de Dole 1676: *Lors conmenta son chamberlenc... Que li aport le heaume ça Qui li fu aportez pieça... Cil ne l'a pas mis en oubli, Ainz l'aport sanz delaier. Quant il l'ot mis hors dou heaumier, Si l'essua d'une touaille;* 1699: *Li serjanz a le heaume pris Quë il avoit maint jor gardé; Quant il l'orent bien esgardé, Il le ra mis en son heaumier*

Exactly what these cases were made from, and their cost, is known from the 1209 and 1213 Misae Rolls of King John's reign. Misae and Liberate Rolls are part of the corpus of the administrative records of medieval England, containing the information primarily on gifts to various people and small personal purchases for the King. An article frequent in these Rolls, and one which rarely gets attention in other written sources, are the orders to manufacture various cases for the storage of King's arms and weapons. The containers mentioned therein are neither particularly complex nor expensive, with prices ranging from 9 to 18 d. per case, suggesting modest or no decoration. In only one case the price reaches 4 s. 6 d (see below). Throughout the Misae Rolls, cases for all sorts of military equipment are generally termed *furrellus*. The specialized helmet case was alternatively called *chapelerum*¹²: "For one helmet case for the storage of King's "arming hats" [i.e. helmets], 18 pennies". Such cases were constructed of cow leather and lined with felt: "For two cases of cow leather, lined with felt, for the storage of two iron helmets used by the King, 26 pennies"¹³, see also footnote 15. The use of multi-layered cases, the inner of cloth and outer of leather, are sometimes suggested; e.g. "For one leather case and one bag of linen cloth, for the storage of King's hauberk and his mail chausses, 9 pennies"¹⁴; then bag was probably put into the unlined leather case. "For four cases of ox leather and four cases of cloth and for the making of those cases, 5 shillings 10 pennies"¹⁵ A possibly higher-quality and thus expensive textile bag is also mentioned, "For one bag of *grisengus* (coarse grey cloth) for the storage of King's armour, lined with linen cloth, 4 shillings 6 pennies."¹⁶ The contemporary Close Rolls tell that *grisengus*, at about 10 d. per ell in, was used as wrapping material for the King's clothing – as we see, it was common in armour storage as well. The message we gather from the knightly romances is that it was prestigious to use a good chest as an outer container: a hauberk, a bejeweled helm and "a rich sword with gilt" kept together in a chest (*coffre*)¹⁷; a similar instance of arms being taken out of an "old chest", *vies cofre*¹⁸. In prose Lancelot (stanza 53), the eponymous knight opens a case/chest (*escrin*) and takes "good arms" out of it¹⁹. Finally, a triple-woven (*treillis*, meaning uncertain) hauberk was kept in an *escrin*, and a polished helmet kept in a "beautiful chest" (*cofre bel et gent*)²⁰.

¹⁰ Romance of Alexander A (AlexParA) II 2824var.: *L'eschiele Tholomé vint après la premiere A une autre bataille Dayron grant et pleniére; Perchael la conduit, qui fu nes de Valmiere, e en haumiére*

¹¹ vv. 2576-2580: *Veïssiez destrousser somiers,/ Et fraimbaus noviaus et entiers/ Par terre sor chapés escourre,/ Et haubers hors glacier et courre,/ Et fetices chances moût blanches.*

¹² Misae roll 1209 p. 134-135, *Pro uno chapelerum ad ponendum chapellos domini Regis ad armandum xviii d.*

¹³ Misae roll 1213 p. 239, *Pro duobus forellis vaccinis furratis filtro ad imponendum duos capellos ferri ad opus domini Regis xxvi. d.*

¹⁴ Misae roll 1213 p. 257, *Pro I forello de corio & pro I sacco de lineo panno ad imponendum loricam domini Regis & caligas ejus de ferro xiiii d.*

¹⁵ Misae roll 1213 p. 235, *Pro iiiior forrellis de corio bovino & iiiior forrellis de pano emptis et pro eisdem forellis faciendis ... v. s. x. d.*

¹⁶ Misae roll 1209 p. 141, *Pro uno sacco de grisenc ad fendas armaturas Regis furruris de linea tela iiii s. vi. d.*

¹⁷ Romance of Parise la Duchesse, p. 143, v.9: *Il deferment .i. coffre que .i. muz or aporte, / S'an traient les auberz et les iaumes gomez,/ Et les espees riches don li pon sont dorez.*

¹⁸ Romance of Fregus, p. 20, v. 12-15: *Li garcons est tost sallies sus... / S'a un vies cofre desfrume, Si et trait unes armes teus / Que jou bien vous sai dire queus.*

¹⁹ : Prose Lancelot, stanza 53: *Lor a ouvert .I. escrin et dist a Lancelot qu'il preingne iluec bones armes et tout ce qu'il couvient.*

²⁰ Romance of Fregus, p. 176, vv. 14-17: *.j. escrin li ont desfrume, / S'en traient .j. auberc treillis, / .j. vert elme d'acier burnis / Traient d'un cofre bel et gent.*

From other purchase orders, however, it would appear as if best armour of the King received leather cases, while the rest was stored in bags of cloth: “Two cases of leather for the storage of hauberks and [a leather case] for the storage of King’s helmet, 6 shillings 7 pennies; two large bags of *chanevacum* (coarse cloth) for eight hauberks, 2 shillings.”²¹ Obviously, John also had some more basic equipment, for which simple barrels sufficed, “...Round barrels for the weapons of the Lord King...”²² Understandably, commoners used all the available containers, as exemplified by the 1240 inventory of Corsican skinner Armannus *pelliparius*: “one sack in which there is a *corellum* (probably a kind of mail hauberk), one barrel in which there is a *barberia* (possibly a helmet with a face mask) and a *manberga* (possibly a hauberk), a basket with a hauberk with mail hood, and three *manbergis*, one *corellum*...”²³

Crossbows and bows were similarly stored and transported in accordance with their price and status of their users. The Misae Rolls provide evidence of something very rare – crossbow cases; “For six cases of cow leather and felt for six crossbows of the lord King, 6 shillings.”²⁴ These were beautiful and high-quality weapons, doubtless much better than the crossbows mass-produced for troops and castle armories. One can see that the construction of these crossbow cases echoes that of King John’s armour cases discussed above. Large stationary crossbows or balistas installed on castle towers were likewise protected from the elements by their covers; a great balista ordered for the tower of the Monreal castle (Navarre) was worth 110 shillings, while its cover (*coopertoria*) and bowstrings cost as much as 19 shillings²⁵. This cover was most likely multi-layered, combining leather and felt or fabric, as it had to withstand the outside conditions. Crossbow bolts were kept in chests, as is well shown in the inventory of the castles of Normandy in the Norman Cartulary: Pont-Audomer had in stock one “chest with quarrels” (*archa cum quarellis*) while Pacy-sur-Seine had “two chests full of quarrels” (*archas plenas quarrellis*)²⁶. A unique reference in the Misae Rolls attests to the use of cloth to cover the bolts in the chest: “For one ell [of unspecified fabric] over the bolts in a chest, 9 pennies.”²⁷

In his PhD thesis, Thomas Richardson includes a very representative account of packing orders for the 1399 Irish expedition of king Richard II. It is worth quoting the whole passage from this thesis: “For packing 3,000 sheaves of arrows, 1,500 bows, 2,880 bowstrings, 200 pavises, 200 long lances, and 359 mail shirts, the packaging comprised twenty long coffers at 3s. 4d., thirty short coffers at 18d. and forty short coffers at 14d. plus 300 nails at 5d. a hundred, 200 nails at 6d. a hundred and 300 nails at 4d. a hundred for fastening them closed, sixty barrels at 8d. each for the mail, forty pipes for arrows and bowstrings, a total of 190 containers of different sorts. Eight workmen were paid 6d. a day for twelve days packing, then for four days carrying the barrels, pipes and coffers to the river. The shipment was then converted into tuns: battilage at Waterford from the ship to the land was 4d. per tun for the eighty tuns. Eighty carts (one tun per

²¹ Misae roll 1209 p. 116, *Duobus furrellis de corio ad loricas ponendas & [furrellus de corio] ad helmum domini Regis ponendas v. s. vii. d. duobus magnis saccis de chanevacum ad octo loricas ponendas ii. s.*

²² Misae roll 1212 p. 258, *...circulis barillos ad armas Domini Regis...*

²³ *Sachum unum in quo est corellum unum ferrei, barilem unam in qua est barberia una cum manberga, panerium unum in quo est osbergum unum cum infula ferrei, et cum tribus manbergis, corellum unum...*

²⁴ p. 114, *Pro sex furrellis de corio vacce & de feltro ad vi. balistas domini Regis vi s.*

²⁵ *Pro balista de garroto, empta ad opus turris Montis Regalis, cx s. Ibi pro faciendo quodam coopertorio ad opus istius baliste de turno, et cordis, xix s.*

²⁶ E. Audouin, “Essai sur l’armée royale au temps de Philippe Auguste”, Paris, 1913, pp. 187-197.

²⁷ Misae roll 1209, p. 131, *Pro una ulna super quarrellos infra cophram xi. d.*

cart) were hired to carry the shipment 40 leagues to Dalkey from Waterford, at 6s. 8d. a cart, another 40 leagues from Dalkey to Kilkenny and another 36 leagues from Kilkenny to Dublin, at a total cost of £26 13s. 8d. per stage.”²⁸ This account deals with the arms gathered for the whole expedition force, possibly excluding King’s own armour and weapons, which would explain the simplicity of packaging. We learn from this text that hauberks were transported in barrels, about six hauberks per barrel so the barrels were relatively small in size. An interesting detail is that the lids of the containers were fixed with nails. In the 10th-11th year of Edward I (1282-1283), the King gives money to Ralph de Stokes for “coffers, bags, boxes and cases, bought to put various armours in them”²⁹, although the number of items involved, or their quality, is not clear.

Figure 2. 1370-1380 Italy, BNF NAF 5243, fol. 26r - Guiron le Courtois. The armour of one of the ventral characters is hung for display, while the valets take his shield out of a leather or textile case. This is the only instance of an armour or weapon case shown in medieval art known to the author

Regarding the transport of military goods by carts, it is worth noting that the service of one cart in Philip August’s army was valued at 13 livres 10 sous, with one cart per every 30-60 sergeants (50 on average). Assuming 20 kg of supplies and weapons per each serjeant, we arrive at 1 ton of

²⁸ Roland Thomas Richardson (2012), The medieval inventories of the Tower armouries 1320–1410 (PhD thesis).

²⁹ *coffris, saccis, bahudis et forellis, emptis pro diversis armaturis imponendis*

load per cart; the packaging of personal goods must have consisted chiefly of sacks as these men were of limited means and likely walked to the muster points, making the use of heavier containers impractical.

Discussion

Several inferences can be made from the above. First, all military equipment was well packaged, in accordance with its value, so that to shelter it from weather variations. The fragile decoration of the more expensive pieces, e.g. gemstones and gilt, required extra protection as well. This aspect of medieval material culture is almost completely missing in medieval visual art, where the intent of the artist is to show the item itself, not the various covers protecting it. Therefore, most of the information on the containers used in packaging and storage of weapons and armour is gathered from written sources.

The following generalized approach to weapon and armour storage can be proposed:

- For the most expensive and valued items, three layers were likely used – (a) costly fabric, usually silk, in which the item itself was wrapped, (b) a case of (cow) leather, lined with felt, (c) a chest or box, probably with some degree of decoration. Several layers of protection ensured prolonged survival of the lords' most prized possessions.
- At the opposite end of the spectrum, there are the poorer people keeping their armour and weapons in whatever sacks, baskets, barrels and chests they possessed. The arms of non-noble men of the castle garrisons may have received equally basic treatment: we are often told of rusty armours in the armouries.
- For long-distance transport of arms and armour by organized units, chests and barrels were used - starting from about the 14th century when small professional forces were becoming more common. The earlier feudal forces must have used less uniform collections of containers, as the smaller units or individuals were responsible for their own packing.
- Siege artillery, such as the stationary winch-spanned balistas, too, were protected by costly covers, as they were installed on the walls and exposed to the varying weather. In all likelihood, these covers or cases were made of leather, with fabric or felt lining similar to the cases of the smaller arms.

Figure 3. ca. 1070-1090 England, Canterbury – The Bayeux Tapestry. The servants are loading the arms and victuals onto the ships for William’s expedition to England. The hauberks, swords, helmets and lances are quite unrealistically carried without any packaging, but the artist’s intention was to show the arms themselves.

Figure 4. ca. 1240-1250, France, Morgan Library, MS M.638, fol. 27v. – the Morgan (Maciejowski) Bible. The miniature shows the carts which brought the military supplies for the war against the Philistines, on the order of King David. One can see aketons, hauberks, shields, knightly helmets, kettle hats piled up in the carts; there are also some sacks. This famous miniature is often used to demonstrate the transport of military supplies, but in author’s opinion it misinforms the viewer. While the carts themselves may be well-represented, the gear, especially the expensive knightly armour, was certainly not carelessly piled up the way shown in this scene. However, the camping gear such as cauldrons and canteens hanging on the sides of the carts may be a realistic feature.

References

Misae Roll of 1209

https://books.google.fi/books?id=ITwLAAAAYAAJ&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false

Misae Roll of 1213

https://books.google.fi/books?id=TUNNAAAACAAJ&pg=PA235&lpg=PA235&dq=%22forellis+faciendis%22&source=bl&ots=tSkSebYdr5&sig=ACfU3U0cG-kPo2ZvOR9DKIER8xjkeZACwA&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjYp7u7j4_4AhWNposKHXMSABkQ6AF6BAgDEAM#v=onepage&q&f=false

A. Schultz. Das höfische Leben zur Zeit der Minnesinger. Leipzig, S. Hirzel, 1899.

<https://archive.org/details/dashfischelebe01schuuoft>

Alekseychik, P. K. (2022). Chests, sacks and cases: the storage of arms and armour in the middle ages. (Preprint)

Histoire de la guerre de Navarre en 1276 et 1277, publiée avec une traduction, une introd. et des notes par Francisque-Michel, Paris, Impr. Imperial, 1856.

https://books.google.fi/books?id=jjM_AAAAcAAJ&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false

1239 will <https://dalme.org/collections/records/65b1080b-62cd-4606-967b-42ac7d1c44fc/58/>

1240 will <https://dalme.org/collections/records/d08f1cc4-54bb-408b-9205-7ed75c496690/246/>

Edouard Audouin, Essai sur l'armée royale au temps de Philippe Auguste, Paris : É. Champion, 1913. <https://archive.org/details/essaisurlarmer00audouoft/page/80/mode/2up>

Roman de Fregus

https://books.google.fi/books?id=1dJAAQAAMAAJ&pg=PA176&lpg=PA176&dq=%22Traient+d%E2%80%99un+cofre+bel+et+gent%22&source=bl&ots=fiH1eyWq1P&sig=ACfU3U0bcXVLF_ou0WD4rRmuqSZZyyrtZw&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjOlby78JH4AhUN6CoKHRu7AgYQ6AF6BAgFEAM#v=onepage&q&f=false

Roman de Lancelot

<https://archive.org/details/leromandelachare00chr/page/n21/mode/2up?q=1%27escrois>

Roman de Berinus

<http://txm.ish-lyon.cnrs.fr/bfm/pdf/Berin1.pdf>

Huon de Bourdele

<https://books.google.fi/books?id=b8yrHFqoOv8C&pg=PA312&lpg=PA312&dq=%22Huon+de+Bourdele%22&source=bl&ots=4XdzvQGyDK&sig=ACfU3U01xPsGbMORTQZ6voDE6tTsypEXUg&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwicq9f4qJP4AhWrs4sKHa5iCBIQ6AF6BAgCEAM#v=onepage&q=%22Huon%20de%20Bourdele%22&f=false>

Aliscans

<https://archive.org/details/aliscanskritisch00alисуoft/page/20/mode/2up?q=elme>

Le Roman de la rose / Guillaume de Dole

<https://archive.org/details/leromandelarose02renagoog/page/n212/mode/2up?q=elmes>

Romance of Alexander A

<https://archive.org/details/liromansdalixan00michgoog/page/28/mode/2up?q=elme>

Roland Thomas Richardson (2012), The medieval inventories of the Tower armouries 1320–1410 (PhD thesis).

https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/3919/1/Thom_Richardson_thesis_final.pdf